

The Hipparcos Catalogue:
Annex of Double and Multiple Stars
(Version 3)

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1. Introduction

The present version of the Annex of Double and Multiple Stars (ADMS) is based on the considerations given in DSWG.LO.004 and the discussions following the first two versions. The main changes are (see attached sample page):

1. allowance for multiple solutions of the same system (Field 2);
2. upper-case letters used to designate components (Field 3);
3. dotted fields (V2) are filled with the relevant data instead;
4. all correlations are relegated to the machine-readable part;
5. relative positions (ρ, θ) given to full precision (Fields 21–22);
6. $\Delta H p$ and $\dot{\theta}$ introduced (Fields 23–24). Note that $360^\circ/\dot{\theta}$ gives an order-of-magnitude estimate of the period of a binary system;
7. A flag 'L' introduced for components with a light-curve in the photometric annex (Field 18);
5. systems are separated by thin horizontal lines.

In addition, key tables are provided for both the printed and the machine-readable annex (Tables 1–4).

2. Data hierarchy

With the introduction of possible multiple solutions there are really four levels of data:

- (1) the top level is the 'system', uniquely identified by a CCDM number. If the system appears in the Hipparcos Input Catalogue (SP-1136, Vol. 6) then the same designation will be used, with (if possible) the same designation of components. Systems discovered by Hipparcos will be given a new CCDM number according to the position (at epoch 1991.25, TBC) of the primary (A = brightest) component;
- (2) the next level is the 'solution'. If there is only one solution (the normal case!) then this level should be practically invisible. Thus, Field 2 is left blank in such cases, whereas for multiple solutions it is given a running number. Note however that there is a corresponding field in the header record of the machine-readable version, which gives the actual number of solutions, i.e., '1' for a unique solution, etc. Note that there must be a predefined maximum number of solutions that can be allowed per system (presently 9, see Table 2);
- (3) the third level is the 'component', designated by letters A, B, ..., if possible chosen consistently with the component designations in the Input Catalogue. By definition (here), a component is unresolved by Hipparcos, i.e., separation less than about 0.15 arcsec. I am still uncertain what to do if the Input Catalogue contains more than one component which in HIP/ADMS must be considered a single component: it is *not* desirable to have a designation like 'BC' for such a component — perhaps it would simply be called 'B' in HIP/ADMS;
- (4) the fourth level is the 'normal point', providing a separate (but not necessarily statistically independent) estimate of the six parameters α , δ , $\mu_{\alpha*}$, μ_{δ} , π , and ΔHp . (Note that the magnitude *must* be included here, as it is often strongly correlated with the position estimate.)

3. Definition of a normal point

In DSWG.LO.004 I proposed that *one* normal point per component should be given for systems with linear motions (including systems with and without differential proper motion), *two* normal points for systems with quadratic motions, *three* for cubic motions, etc. This is the minimum number of normal points, but it is of course quite feasible — without any change of format! — to give as many normal points as desired. For instance, it may be better to give *three* normal points for quadratic motions: the position part of these normal points could more readily be used as input e.g. to a *posteriori* orbit determinations (the proper motions, although given in the catalogue, could then be discarded as providing no additional information).

4. Correlations

In the present draft version the printed Annex contains no correlations whatsoever. This is not because correlations are less important than in the main catalogue (indeed, they are probably more important here!), but because there are so many possible correlations and it would be very difficult to select only a few of them. Each normal point contains six estimated parameters, and with N_d lines of data (components $\times$ normal points) there may be up to $6N_d(6N_d - 1)/2$ correlation coefficients. The format of the machine-readable Annex allows all these coefficients to be given. In most cases one or several parameters (typically π and $H\rho$, sometimes μ_{α^*} and μ_{δ}) are constrained to be the same for different components and/or epochs; this is indicated by a correlation coefficient equal to +1.00.

5. The systems on the sample page

The data on the sample page have been filled in more or less at random, without regard to any real systems or even the consistency between the different columns. They are only intended to give an impression of the layout for a few different types of systems:

20512+5126: A simple binary with linear differential motion

20514-0537: A binary with quadratic motions — three normal points are given for each component

20531+2909: An unresolved astrometric binary, detected by its non-linear proper motion. Two normal points are given (it could have been three instead!)

21014-7526: An optical binary. For this system there are individual entries in the main catalogue, so there might be some specific reason for including it in the Annex, e.g., to specify the correlations between the parameters of the two components

21114+3526: A system with three more or less equally probable solutions: a well-separated binary, a close binary, or a triple star. The machine-readable Annex gives some indication of the goodness-of-fit of each solution, but this is not included in the printed Annex: all solutions necessarily give 'reasonable' fits, and the user could hardly make a better ranking of the solutions than the reduction consortia

21514-1529: A triple star with linear differential motions

Component CCDM	HIP	Epoch J1900+	Position at Epoch		Prop. Motion		Par. π mas	Standard Errors						Mag. & Colour			Relative Data				
			α deg	δ deg	$\mu_{\alpha*}$ mas/yr	μ_{δ} mas/yr		$\sigma_{\alpha*}$ mas	σ_{δ} mas	$\sigma_{\alpha**}$ mas	$\sigma_{\mu_{\alpha*}}$ mas/yr	$\sigma_{\mu_{\delta}}$ mas	σ_{π} mas	H_p mag	σ_{H_p} mag	$V-I$ mag	θ deg	ρ arcsec	ΔH_p mag	$\dot{\theta}$ deg/yr	
1	2 3 4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
20512+5126	A 102921	91.173	312.782 293 70	+51.432 876 19	-52.3	41.7	38.5	2.7	3.3	0.5	1.3	2.0	7.301	0.009	0.795						
	B 102921	91.173	312.782 401 27	+51.432 711 21	-51.1	41.9	38.5	6.5	8.5	2.6	2.9	2.0	10.048	0.067	0.795	A	36.11	0.912	2.747	0.37	
20514-0537	A 102945	90.470	312.793 393 70	-05.459 676 19	96.5	-7.1	9.1	3.1	3.6	2.1	2.0	3.0	6.4	0.16	V 0.376						
		91.398	312.793 397 35	-05.459 678 89	94.1	-7.8	9.1	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.2	3.0	6.4	0.16	V 0.376						
		92.247	312.793 401 26	-05.459 680 61	92.8	-7.9	9.1	3.6	3.6	3.7	3.4	3.0	6.4	0.16	V 0.376						
	B 102945	90.470	312.793 500 47	-05.459 510 30	85.2	13.9	9.1	8.6	9.5	3.8	3.9	3.0	7.582	0.075	0.376	A	219.6	0.338	1.2	1.6	
		91.398	312.793 504 21	-05.459 512 92	88.7	11.8	9.1	7.9	9.1	5.7	5.2	3.0	7.582	0.075	0.376	A	222.8	0.340	1.2	1.7	
		92.247	312.793 507 39	-05.459 513 99	89.1	11.1	9.1	8.1	8.7	5.1	5.0	3.0	7.582	0.075	0.376	A	224.2	0.341	1.2	1.7	
20531+2909	A 103074	90.391	313.023 239 81	+29.156 212 23	-130.2	210.5	105.2	1.9	2.1	2.5	2.8	1.1	8.212	0.006	1.012						
		92.155	313.023 241 16	+29.156 331 95	-125.1	213.6	105.2	2.0	2.2	2.7	3.1	1.1	8.212	0.006	1.012						
21014-7526	A 103745	91.314	315.012 301 81	-75.391 376 19	52.3	-64.1	5.1	2.7	3.3	0.5	1.3	2.0	8.510	0.019	0.108						
	B 103747	91.314	315.012 118 17	-75.391 811 21	91.1	13.2	-1.1	6.5	8.5	2.6	2.9	2.4	9.73	0.07	V 0.477	A	157.811	13.016	1.22	-0.123	
21114+3526	1 A 104510	91.112	315.012 301 81	+35.391 376 19	22.3	-11.5	3.1	3.7	3.3	2.2	1.9	2.1	9.610	0.049	0.501						
	B 104510	91.112	315.012 118 17	+35.391 811 21	22.3	-11.5	3.1	3.7	3.3	2.2	1.9	2.1	11.933	0.150	L 0.501	A	29.39	3.812	2.323		
	2 A 104510	91.112	315.012 301 70	+35.391 376 34	22.1	-11.0	5.2	3.6	3.4	2.4	2.2	2.2	9.621	0.043	0.501						
	B 104510	91.112	315.012 117 65	+35.391 811 20	22.1	-11.0	5.2	3.6	3.4	2.4	2.2	2.2	11.641	0.135	0.501	A	27.4	0.421	2.020		
	3 A 104510	91.112	315.012 301 61	+35.391 376 40	22.0	-10.1	4.5	3.8	3.5	2.6	2.3	2.3	9.642	0.068	0.501						
	B 104510	91.112	315.012 118 08	+35.391 811 91	22.0	-10.1	4.5	3.8	3.5	2.6	2.3	2.3	11.915	0.150	0.501	A	27.4	0.421	2.273		
	C 104510	91.112	315.012 153 65	+35.391 618 20	22.0	-10.1	4.5	3.8	3.5	2.6	2.3	2.3	13.14	0.48	0.501	A	172.81	2.201	3.502		
21514-1529	A 107624	91.240	315.754 271 04	-15.482 117 88	196.5	-81.9	49.1	2.0	1.8	2.5	2.2	2.4	6.391	0.021	0.814						
	B 107624	91.240	315.754 118 38	-15.482 141 20	196.7	-83.2	49.1	2.8	2.5	3.1	3.0	2.4	7.582	0.087	0.814	A	341.055	15.513	1.191	-0.208	
	C 107624	91.240	315.753 845 51	-15.482 333 46	188.9	-81.0	49.1	4.9	4.2	5.2	5.0	2.4	7.912	0.121	0.814	B	102.0	0.833	0.330	1.2	

Annex of Double and Multiple Stars: The Printed Catalogue

Table 1. Key to the Printed Annex of Double and Multiple Stars

Field	Content	Page (Vol. 6)
1	System identifier (CCDM number; ERF 2000, epoch 1991.25 [TBC])	xx
2	Solution identifier: (blank) = only one solution was found 1, 2, ... = running number for multiple solutions	xx
3	Component identifier (letters A, B, C, ...)	xx
4	Hipparcos Catalogue (HIP) running number under which the component was observed	xx
5	Epoch to which all data on this line refer (year - J1900)	xx
6	Right ascension (epoch as in Field 5, ERF 2000), α (degrees)	xx
7	Declination (epoch as in Field 5, ERF 2000), δ (degrees)	xx
8	Proper motion in right ascension (epoch as in Field 5, ERF 2000), μ_{α^*} (milli-arcsec/year)	xx
9	Proper motion in declination (epoch as in Field 5, ERF 2000), μ_{δ} (milli-arcsec/year)	xx
10	Trigonometric parallax, π (milli-arcsec)	xx
11	Standard error of position in right ascension (epoch as in Field 5), σ_{α^*} (milli-arcsec)	xx
12	Standard error of position in declination (epoch as in Field 5), σ_{δ} (milli-arcsec)	xx
13	Standard error of proper motion in right ascension (epoch as in Field 5), $\sigma_{\mu_{\alpha^*}}$ (milli-arcsec/year)	xx
14	Standard error of proper motion in declination (epoch as in Field 5), $\sigma_{\mu_{\delta}}$ (milli-arcsec/year)	xx
15	Standard error of the trigonometric parallax, σ_{π} (milli-arcsec)	xx
16	Median magnitude of component in the Hipparcos photometric system, H_p (mag)	xx
17	Standard error of the median H_p magnitude, σ_{H_p} (mag)	xx
18	Variability flag: V = component is probably variable L = a (folded) light curve of component is included in Volume 8	xx
19	Colour index (from ground-based observations) used for astrometric reductions, $V - I$ (mag)	xx
20	Reference component for the data in Fields 21-24	xx
21	Position angle relative to reference component (epoch as in Field 5), θ (degrees)	xx
22	Separation from reference component (epoch as in Field 5), ρ (arcsec)	xx
23	Median magnitude difference (present component minus reference component), ΔH_p (mag)	xx
24	Rate of change of position angle relative to reference component, $\dot{\theta}$ (degrees/year)	xx

Note: $\sigma_{\alpha^*} = \sigma_{\alpha} \cos \delta$, $\mu_{\alpha^*} = \mu_{\alpha} \cos \delta$

Annex of Double and Multiple Stars: Additional Machine-Readable Data

In the machine-readable version of the Annex of Double and Multiple Stars, the data for each system (uniquely identified by a CCDM number) are organized into several sequential records. For a system with multiple solutions the record structure can be schematically represented as follows:

The header record contains, in addition to the CCDM number, fields describing the number of solutions and the number of data records and cross-correlation records for each solution. The fields of the header record are defined in Table 2. The format allows for at most nine (TBC) solutions.

Each data record contains information related to one normal point, i.e., a single component as reduced to fixed epoch. There is exactly one data record for each line of data in the printed Annex. The first 24 fields are identical to Fields 1–24 of the printed Annex, except that fields 1–4 are filled in with the relevant identifiers whenever they are blank in the printed Annex. The following fields, which appear only in the machine-readable version, are defined in Table 3. Note that the data records of a given solution are sequentially numbered (Field 26) $i_d = 1, 2, \dots, N_d$ irrespective of the component or epoch. The integer N_d is given in the header record.

Each cross-correlation record contains the correlation coefficients for all 36 possible combinations of the estimated parameters in two different data records (within the same solution). The first two fields specify which data records are considered (i, j , with $1 \leq i < j \leq N_d$). There can be at most $N_d(N_d - 1)/2$ cross-correlation records in a solution with N_d data records. The fields of the cross-correlation record are defined in Table 4.

Table 2. Header Record

Field	Content	Page (Vol. 6)
1	System identifier (CCDM number)	xx
2	Number of solutions, N_s	xx
3	Number of components in solution #1, $N_c(1)$	xx
4	Number of data records in solution #1, $N_d(1)$	xx
5	Number of cross-correlation records in solution #1, $N_r(1)$	xx
6	Goodness-of-fit statistic for solution #1	
7	Number of components in solution #2, $N_c(2)$	
8	Number of data records in solution #2, $N_d(2)$	
9	Number of cross-correlation records in solution #2, $N_r(2)$	
10	Goodness-of-fit statistic for solution #2	
	⋮	
35	Number of components in solution #9, $N_c(9)$	
36	Number of data records in solution #9, $N_d(9)$	
37	Number of cross-correlation records in solution #9, $N_r(9)$	
38	Goodness-of-fit statistic for solution #9	

Table 3. Data Record (see Table 1 for Fields 1–24)

Field	Content	Page (Vol. 6)
25	Sequential number of the solution, i_s ($1 \leq i_s \leq N_s$)	xx
26	Sequential number of the data record within the solution, i_d ($1 \leq i_d \leq N_d(i_s)$)	xx
27	Correlation coefficient r_{12}	xx
28	Correlation coefficient r_{13}	
29	Correlation coefficient r_{14}	
30	Correlation coefficient r_{15}	
31	Correlation coefficient r_{16}	
32	Correlation coefficient r_{23}	
33	Correlation coefficient r_{24}	
34	Correlation coefficient r_{25}	
35	Correlation coefficient r_{26}	
36	Correlation coefficient r_{34}	
37	Correlation coefficient r_{35}	
38	Correlation coefficient r_{36}	
39	Correlation coefficient r_{45}	
40	Correlation coefficient r_{46}	
41	Correlation coefficient r_{56}	

Note: indices 1–6 refer to the estimated parameters in the following sequence: $\alpha, \delta, \mu_{\alpha*}, \mu_\delta, \pi, Hp$

Table 4. Cross-Correlation Record

Field	Content	Page (Vol. 6)
1	First data record identifier, i ($1 \leq i < N_d$)	xx
2	Second data record identifier, j ($i < j \leq N_d$)	xx
3	Correlation coefficient $r_{11}(i, j)$	xx
4	Correlation coefficient $r_{12}(i, j)$	
5	Correlation coefficient $r_{13}(i, j)$	
6	Correlation coefficient $r_{14}(i, j)$	
7	Correlation coefficient $r_{15}(i, j)$	
8	Correlation coefficient $r_{16}(i, j)$	
9	Correlation coefficient $r_{21}(i, j)$	
10	Correlation coefficient $r_{22}(i, j)$	
11	Correlation coefficient $r_{23}(i, j)$	
12	Correlation coefficient $r_{24}(i, j)$	
13	Correlation coefficient $r_{25}(i, j)$	
14	Correlation coefficient $r_{26}(i, j)$	
15	Correlation coefficient $r_{31}(i, j)$	
16	Correlation coefficient $r_{32}(i, j)$	
17	Correlation coefficient $r_{33}(i, j)$	
18	Correlation coefficient $r_{34}(i, j)$	
19	Correlation coefficient $r_{35}(i, j)$	
20	Correlation coefficient $r_{36}(i, j)$	
21	Correlation coefficient $r_{41}(i, j)$	
22	Correlation coefficient $r_{42}(i, j)$	
23	Correlation coefficient $r_{43}(i, j)$	
24	Correlation coefficient $r_{44}(i, j)$	
25	Correlation coefficient $r_{45}(i, j)$	
26	Correlation coefficient $r_{46}(i, j)$	
27	Correlation coefficient $r_{51}(i, j)$	
28	Correlation coefficient $r_{52}(i, j)$	
29	Correlation coefficient $r_{53}(i, j)$	
30	Correlation coefficient $r_{54}(i, j)$	
31	Correlation coefficient $r_{55}(i, j)$	
32	Correlation coefficient $r_{56}(i, j)$	
33	Correlation coefficient $r_{61}(i, j)$	
34	Correlation coefficient $r_{62}(i, j)$	
35	Correlation coefficient $r_{63}(i, j)$	
36	Correlation coefficient $r_{64}(i, j)$	
37	Correlation coefficient $r_{65}(i, j)$	
38	Correlation coefficient $r_{66}(i, j)$	

Note: $r_{mn}(i, j)$ is the correlation coefficient between the m th parameter of the i th data record, and the n th parameter of the j th data record